

Co-aligning the EIS flare data from 9 March 2012 with AIA images

Data preparation

The JSOC cutout service was used to download AIA 94 Å sub-images of size 500" x 500" at full cadence for the period 03:32 to 03:41 UT. The corresponding “spikes” files were also downloaded.

The AIA images were “respiked” using the routine `aia_cutout_respike`:

```
IDL> aia_cutout_respike, aia_files, spike=spike_files
```

The EIS data file beginning at 03:09 UT was calibrated to level-1, and a *windata* structure was created for the the Fe XIV $\lambda 274.20$ line. A IDL map for this line was also created:

```
IDL> wd=eis_getwindata(file,274.20,/refill)
```

```
IDL> eis_make_image,file,274.20,fe14,/map
```

Creating synthetic AIA rasters

The rapid evolution of the flare ribbon coupled with the relatively slow step rate of the EIS raster makes coalignment of AIA and EIS difficult. The procedure is to create a synthetic raster from the AIA images that mimics an EIS raster image of a similar temperature.

The IDL routine `aia_make_eis_raster.pro` was created for this purpose. For each EIS exposure it does the following steps:

- Create an empty image of the same size as the EIS raster image.
- Find the AIA maps that lie between the start/end times of an exposure.
- Convolve each AIA map with a 2D Gaussian kernel with a FWHM of 3" (to mimic the lower spatial resolution of EIS).
- Rebin the AIA map to match the EIS y-pixel size using `rebin_map.pro` (the data are not rebinned in x, however).
- Find the AIA data columns within the EIS slit position and add them to the empty raster image. If there are multiple maps for an exposure, average the data columns from these maps.
- Repeat for each EIS exposure.

The call to the routine is:

```
IDL> map=aia_make_eis_raster(files,wd,/clean,offset=offset,eis_map=fe14)
```

where “files” is the list of respiked AIA 94 Å cutout files. The input “offset” is used to specify a spatial offset between EIS and AIA. The x-offset is adjusted to improve the comparison between the AIA synthetic raster image and the EIS image.

The routine `aia_make_eis_raster` is available from the GitHub repository <https://github.com/pryoung/sdo-idl>.

Results

Figure 1 shows the synthetic AIA raster images generated by `aia_make_eis_raster`, compared to the EIS Fe XIV 274.20 raster image (top-left). The numbers on the EIS image indicate the exposure numbers – one for each column of the image. The spectrum used in the paper was created from exposure 57.

The routine `aia_make_eis_raster` was run for eight values of the EIS-AIA x-offset, which are indicated in the top-left of each of the eight AIA images.

Figure 1. The top-left image shows the EIS Fe XIV 274.20 raster image. The remaining nine panels are synthetic raster images formed from AIA 94 A images (see main text).

In assessing these images, our main criterion is that the brightening on the left side of the images should be reproduced reasonably well. It is clear that offsets of $x < -2.0$ do not work. The simulated slit of AIA is too far to the left of the brightening to give a useful signal.

Offsets of 1.0 and higher also do not work as the brightening has the peak brightness in exposure 59, whereas the EIS data have the peak in exposure 58.

Considering the morphology of the brightening, offset -1.5 best reproduces the EIS image. However, the brightening is somewhat weaker compared to the emission on the right side of the image. The contrast is better for offsets -1.0 and 0.0, but the emission in exposure 57 is weaker than in the EIS image.

Conclusion

I conclude that the offset -1.5 is the best. The intensity discrepancy between the left and right sides may be due to a temperature difference, perhaps caused by Fe XVIII in the 94 Å channel (which we believe is not present in the brightening).